

FOUR COMPETENCY PERSPECTIVES IN LEARNING ENGLISH

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Abstract

The English language has penetrated to all corners of the globe. At that time, the most important task for England was to establish trade relations. Naturally, the language of the dominant and more developed country relegated local languages to the background. The golden rule worked here - whoever has the gold rules, he chooses which language to speak. The English language has penetrated to all corners of the globe. At that time, the most important task for England was to establish trade relations. Naturally, the language of the dominant and more developed country relegated local languages to the background. The golden rule worked here - whoever has the gold rules, he chooses which language to speak. This prestigious language is extracting attention to itself as a language of virtue throwing up lavish possibilities it offers to a person for prosperity and advancement in life. English as a second language (ESL) turns out to be unavoidable as well as inescapable in the Indian education structure. To learn a second language, a psychological and emotional participation is required to communicate forcefully and to elucidate linguistic signification. The motive of this study is to be acquainted with the importance of making use of all skills in learning English. The four basic skills of learning a language are Listening, Speaking, Reading and Writing. These are the four potentialities that authorise a person to assimilate, construct and make use of the language in a meaningful social conversation. The teacher is required to apply an array of techniques to integrate the necessities of the students. The teacher mixes these techniques throughout the procedure of learning and applies them towards the progressive advancement of proficiency as well as self-confidence of the student in improving the efficacy of this cognitive operation.

Key words

Skills, listening, speaking, reading, writing.

INTRODUCTION

English is a cosmopolitan language. The significance of this highly dignified language cannot be ignored. This is the language of the foremost reputed

universities of the world and is contemplated as the language of higher education. English establishes its predominance in every domain like science, technology, media, global trade, economics, business, tourism, information technology etc. This is an absolutely necessary attribute to be inculcated by a worldwide workforce. Crossing the boundaries of England, USA, Australia, or other territories of the indigenous speakers of English, it has now accomplished the ranking of a universal language that distinctly pinpoints the preeminence of English as a world language. In fact, gone are the days to reckon English as an overseas language as it is deployed at every phase of our life as a second language or official language. Genuinely, about 300 million people employ English as their first language while another 350 million people elsewhere the world utilises English as their second language. It is official or semi-official language in more than 60 countries. It is transformed into the primary language of the enlightenment era that we are now living in. Essentially, learning English is acknowledged as a "must".

Language is an extremely influential tool of expression. It is near impossible to envision about a society sans language. It polishes up people's reasoning, leads and rules their complete vocation. This is the conveyor of civilisation as well as culture. In its manifestation of mother tongue, an individual learns it comfortably. Nevertheless, learning a second language calls for keen endeavours to learn it and the scope of learning a second language in most instances is restricted.

IMPORTANT SKILLS

Language is a complicated expertise, based on four important skills –

- Listening
- Speaking
- Reading
- Writing

These four foundational skills LSRW (Listening, Speaking, Reading, and Writing) may be additionally indexed into two parts: -

Language Skills:

Productive Skills (Active Skills)	Speaking
	Writing
Receptive Skills (Passive Skills)	Listening
	Reading

Speech perception is the receptive skill of the oral phraseology. When we speak of listening what we actually mean is hearing and comprehending. When we hear our mother tongue or first language being spoken, we have all the skills and

background knowledge to understand what we hear; so we probably are not even aware of how complex a process it is.

Listening is a means of language communication which is applied almost extensively in everyday lives of people. Moreover, instructing the students about countless listening exercises is an effective vehicle of augmenting their vocabulary. Additionally, it also assists the students upgrade their listening and perception. For instance, people realise that the huge distinction between first language learning and second language learning lies in their surroundings. For a second language, we can encounter it only in validated location and classes. Tutoring as well as rehearsing the oral reading is not a day's performance. Practice is essential. Only by practising the learners can improve their listening and perception. Speaking is the productive skill in the mode.

Speaking:

Speaking is the productive skill of the oral phraseology. It is like the speaker producing presentations in the oral mode retrieving words and phrases from memory. It is more complicated than it seems initially and necessitates more than just articulating a term.

Reciprocal speaking circumstances comprise person to person discussions and phone calls, in which people are temporarily listening and speaking, including having an opportunity to query for elucidation, replication of words and phrases from their discussion associate. Certain speaking circumstances are moderately interactive like delivering a lecture to a live listener, where the protocol is that the listener does not punctuate the lecture. The speaker, in spite of that can watch the listeners and judge from their facial expressions as well as response whether or not the speech is being comprehended. But a few speaking circumstances may be completely non-interactive, like when recording a conversation for a radio broadcast. Speaking is frequently associated with listening. For instance, the double way transmission makes up for the deficiency in transitive capability in the conventional learning. Double way means the connection of the transmission between the instructors and the pupils at school. This association is attached with the transitive interaction between two individuals. This can generate an energetic atmosphere for speaking language. This double way transmission can extend the dialogue unlimitedly. This is the benefit of it. Simultaneously, if the speakers desire to offer accurate responses, they have to apply mind deeply, the sentences are not calmly ignored being framed by themselves using intelligence, occasionally with the clue of the instructor. They can speak candidly as well as express themselves.

Reading:

This is about the receptive skill in the written mode. It can advance the reader's language skills and improve on his/her listening as well as speaking skills, especially in communities with a rich literary tradition. Reading can assist to enrich one's vocabulary that assists other receptive skills like listening understanding.

Reading is a salient way of acquiring finesse in language learning besides being a basic tool of learning for a student of language. Reading is a common activity in an examination, nowadays. Nevertheless, such readings must be done in restricted time period. Students are required to read a piece appropriately at a definite pace. For example, somebody pronounces word by word. Somebody reads with his finger gliding along successive words in a quivering voice. They often read phrase by phrase shaking head or blinking eyes frequently with moving eyeballs. In the process for better learning of words, there must be reasonable interspaces between their eyes as well as the reading material.

Writing:

This is the productive skill in the written mode. It is little more intricate than it apparently appears, to start with. It usually appears to be the most rigid of the skills even for vernacular speakers of a language, since it envisages not just a pictorial reproduction of spoken words, but the process involves representation of the thought process in an organised manner.

Writing is a process of a demonstrative classroom method. It equips a student to express ideas with cohesion and coherence and learn progressively to calculate his refinement. This helps the writer to build up their grip over lexicon and form and to brush up other language skills. Writing sentences is the foundation of writing an article. Consequently, he ought to start his writing with writing meaningful sentences. Additionally, it also involves skill of translation, altering of sentence pattern, as well as punctuation and rewriting of a text. It assists to comprehend a given text and write compositions thereon. This can enhance the capability of the student to summarise and to make use of the language constructively.

SIGNIFICANCE

The present paper will offer assistance to the teachers, guardians and the authorities concerned for a finer appreciation of the students' challenges in learning English language.

This paper will be advantageous for realising the importance of the basic skills of a language.

The paper will be a helping hand for the forthcoming researchers to go forward with the researches in this domain.

CONCLUSION

The four foundational language skills listening, speaking, reading and writing never are independent zones but all the four together, holistically describes language learning as a discipline. The first and the third are comprehension skills and the second and the fourth are production skills. There is a basic and reciprocal relationship between oral language skills of listening and speaking as is there between the two written language skills of reading and writing. In this transactional world, mastery over a language, more specifically English, the real global language, can determine one's success in life. Consequently, to develop complete communication capability, mastering the four language skills of listening, speaking, reading and writing are profoundly important for effective exchanges of information and ideas.

REFERENCES:

1. Lorena Manaj Sadiku. "The Importance of Four Skills Reading, Speaking, Writing, Listening in a Lesson Hour". European Journal of Language and Literature Studies. Vol. 1, No. 1, 2015.
2. Abdel-Rahman Al-Eiadeh¹, Dr. Mahmoud A. A. Sobh, Dr.Samer M. Al-Zoubi, Dr.Fadi Al-Khasawneh. "Improving English Language Speaking Skills of Ajloun National University Students". International Journal of English and Education. Vol. 5, Issue. 3, 2016.
3. Ms. Chitra Sharma,Dr. Shaifali Rachna Puri, The importance of four basic skills in learning English. The Genesis. ISSN 2395-2164. Volume: 7 Issue: 4. 2020. P-33-36. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.47211/tg.2020.v07i04.007>
4. Султонова, С. Х., & Насириддинова, М. М. (2023). Использование цифровых технологий в практике преподавания русского языка как иностранного (на примере онлайн-доски). *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 1(9), 1346-1352.
5. Султонова, С. Х. (2022, april). Коммуникативные аспекты в методике преподавании рки в школах узбекистана. In *international journal of conference series on education and social sciences (online)* (vol. 2, no. 3).
6. Султонова, Сайёра Холмирзаевна. "обучение научным терминам на занятиях по русскому языку как иностранному." *finland international scientific journal of education, social science & humanities* 11, no. 1 (2023): 777-784.
7. Султонова, С. Х. (2023). Синтаксические конструкции на уроках русского языка как иностранного. *O'zbekistonda fanlararo innovatsiyalar va*

ilmiy tadqiqotlar jurnali, 2(15), 769-775.

8. Султонова, С. Х. (2022, april). Коммуникативные аспекты в методике преподавании рки в школах узбекистана. In international journal of conference series on education and social sciences (online) (vol. 2, no. 3).

9. Султонова, С. Х. (2021). Учебно-речевая ситуация при обучении русскому языку узбекских учащихся элементарного и базового уровней. Русское слово в международном образовательном пространстве: история и современность, 437.